

DESTINATION EARTH CO-DESIGN TOOLKIT

Worksheet 4

The outcomes diagram

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document focuses on Phase #4 of the co-design process, which corresponds to the formalisation of co-design outcomes. It introduces the Outcomes Diagram, a synthesis tool designed to capture, structure, and communicate the portfolio of actions, projects, and relationships emerging from the co-design process. By organising these outcomes in a clear and visual way, the diagram helps turn distributed insights and partial agreements into a shared, strategic representation of “what happens next” for each stakeholder.

Building on the technical and collaborative insights and achievements across all previous phases and used iteratively throughout the co-design workshops, the outcomes diagram transforms discussions and exploratory ideas into a coherent roadmap. It provides an operational framework for aligning stakeholders around shared objectives, clarifying the modalities of collaboration, and identifying concrete next steps across multiple time horizons (short-, mid-, and long-term). In doing so, it supports the construction of a dynamic project portfolio rather than a single isolated service or collaboration, which is central to the resilient-fit approach promoted by the DestinE Co-design.

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1. Introduction to the Outcomes Phase

1.1. Introduction to the Phase #4 - Outcomes phase

The fourth phase of the co-design process focuses on the formalization and continuous structuring of outcomes generated throughout the co-design journey. While it culminates in a final synthesis of achievements, its purpose extends beyond closing the process. The Outcomes Diagram introduced in this phase should be understood as a dynamic tool, used iteratively across all phases to progressively capture the results, commitments, and perspectives emerging from each workshop into a portfolio of possibilities and opportunities.

Throughout the co-design process (during the usefulness, operability, or usability workshops) new insights, partnerships, and project ideas are constantly generated. The Outcomes Diagram provides a structured space to record and update these evolving elements, allowing service providers and users to visualize how short-term actions connect with mid- and long-term opportunities. In this sense, it acts as a compass for collective progress, ensuring that each stage of the process contributes to a coherent and resilient trajectory.

At the end of the co-design process, the diagram is consolidated into its final version. This synthesis formalizes the main outcomes of the collaboration, clarifies ongoing commitments, and identifies the next steps for each stakeholder—whether related to service deployment, further research, partnership development, or scalability.

1.2. Position of outcomes diagram within co-design workflow

The Outcomes Diagram constitutes the final deliverable from the co-design sessions. It synthesizes the key objectives and actions identified by the partners and opens the way for future, on-going and resilient relationships. It stands at very end of the co-design toolchain but should be kept in perspective during the series of co-design workshops that are organized with users and potential partners.

1.3. Objectives

The Outcomes Diagram is a core tool of the DestinE co-design process. Its primary role is to foster a *resilient fit* between the service developer and its user communities.

Unlike a quick-fit approach that may only address immediate user needs, the resilient-fit approach ensures sustainable and adaptive service development by exploring a broader spectrum of potential use cases, cooperation modalities, and time horizons. In line with this perspective, the outcomes diagram ensures that the services developed are resilient, user-centric, and aligned with long-term strategic goals. By integrating diverse user perspectives, formalizing cooperative frameworks, and maintaining a dynamic, iterative approach, the diagram enables a service to adapt and thrive within a complex usage ecosystem. As such, this tool pursues several objectives:

1. **Synthesize Co-design achievements:** It aims to consolidate all key findings and insights from the co-design process, providing a comprehensive representation of user needs, service opportunities, and collaboration frameworks. It transforms complex workshop outputs into an actionable, visual summary that highlights progress and strategic priorities.
2. **Strengthen stakeholder engagement:** The diagram serves as a shared frame of reference that evolves throughout the co-design process. It is progressively populated as workshops unfold, helping to formalize cooperation modalities, align expectations, and maintain a transparent view of ongoing commitments. By continuously updating

this shared visual map, all stakeholders can clarify their roles, identify complementary actions, and build trust over time. This iterative use of the diagram reinforces engagement, ensuring that collaboration frameworks are not defined only at the end of the process, but co-constructed and adjusted as relationships mature.

3. **Provide a strategic roadmap:** The outcomes diagram operates as an evolving roadmap that aligns with the co-design process. It helps the service developer and users jointly situate their perspectives across short-, mid-, and long-term horizons, connecting immediate workshop outcomes with broader strategic ambitions. By revisiting and refining the diagram after each key session, participants can anticipate future developments, sequence activities, and prioritize resources in a coordinated way. The final consolidated version at the end of Phase #4 formalizes this trajectory, translating the iterative co-design work into a coherent and actionable long-term vision.

1.4. Context of Use

The Outcomes Diagram has been tested successfully across multiple cases with diverse service providers in the context of co-design. It has demonstrated its efficiency in structuring collaborative efforts, aligning stakeholder perspectives, and ensuring a resilient fit between services and their user communities. By facilitating the synthesis of insights, formalizing cooperation modalities, and defining strategic roadmaps, the tool has proven to be a valuable asset in navigating complex service development environments. Its adaptability across different use cases confirms its relevance in fostering sustainable, user-centric, and strategically aligned service solutions.

2. Presentation of the tool

The Outcomes Diagram visually represents the results of the co-design workshops, mapping potential services and cooperation modalities across different time horizons. It reflects the dynamic and evolving nature of the co-design process by capturing development perspectives, associated stakeholders, and actionable insights as they emerge. The diagram should be progressively filled throughout the series of workshops, allowing the service developer to consolidate and visualize outcomes at each stage.

At the end of each phase (Usefulness, Operability, and Usability) the diagram should be reviewed and presented to participants as a basis for discussion and validation. This ensures a shared understanding of progress, clarifies next steps, and maintains continuity between phases. The diagram thus evolves in parallel with the co-design process, culminating in a final synthesis at the end of Phase #4 that formalizes the collective achievements and defines pathways for scalability and future collaboration.

2.1. How to use

The outcomes diagram should be used to capture and categorize all potential use cases and collaborative project derived from the co-design process using the blank template (see *template 4.0.1*) shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Blank template for the Outcomes Diagram

Overall, filling in this diagram involves summarizing the co-design results by distinguishing for each different outcome:

- 1) Their time horizon,
- 2) The type of outcomes they correspond to,
- 3) The stakeholder responsible for each outcome,
- 4) The types of action they involve.

Each box represents a specific collaborative perspective, detailing the type of project, the relevant time horizon, and the collaborative path. Together, these outcomes constitute a consistent project portfolio supporting resilient relationships. Ideally, filling in the diagram should reveal the connections between these different elements both across time and among the various categories of projects envisioned.

2.1.1. Time Horizons (X-Axis)

In the diagram, the **X-axis represents time horizons** for the various outcomes of the co-design process. This ensures a clear temporal framework, allowing both the service developer and stakeholders to align their expectations with the projected timelines and foster subsequent relationships/opportunities.

The more detailed the time horizon, the more consistent the diagram, but a precise time horizon may be difficult to define for each outcome. Therefore, at least three temporal perspectives can be taken into account to structure the portfolio in time:

- **Short-term:** Clearly defined an actionable use case that can immediately proceed to development.
- **Mid-term:** Use cases with partially defined expectations that require further clarification or preparatory work before development can begin.
- **Long-term:** Broad, strategic needs with unclear expectations that serve as a foundation for long-term exploration and service evolution.

INSIGHT: Different time scale can be explored during the workshops themselves

Guiding questions can be used during workshops to explore user needs across different time scales and ensure forward-looking discussions. Also, encouraging users to think beyond current constraints and consider future scenarios where DestinE services can help them to formulate consistent needs. Here are some instances of guiding questions tailored to DestinE's and service providers strategic objectives:

1. Exploring immediate potential:

- What immediate value do you see in the services demonstrated?
- How could this service integrate into your current workflows?

2. Mid- and Long-term exploration:

- Beyond immediate needs, what future scenarios or challenges could benefit from a DestinE service?
- What types of data or insights would you require to address these challenges?

3. Exploration beyond constraints:

- If resource or technological constraints were removed, what ideal data-based services would you envision?
- What new collaborations could further enrich the service?

2.1.2. Type of outcomes (Y-axis)

The **Y-axis aims to distinguish between different categories of outcomes based on what the service developer aims to achieve with the users.** These categories are tailored to the specific context and objectives of their relationships. Thus, they can be adapted for each co-design initiative. This adaptability of the Y-axis ensures that the Outcomes Diagram remains a flexible to the specific collaborative context, to capture a wide range of co-design outcomes while always mapping them against their corresponding time horizons. However, some generic categories can be considered by default, related to the usual outcomes of service development in the context of DestinE services¹ :

- 1) **Monitoring system** when the user only needs to monitor a certain variable or phenomenon - information is then complemented by visualization tools and other customized tools depending on user's operations.

Ex: monitoring pollutant concentrations.

- 2) **Decision support system:** monitoring system complemented with other customized tools based on specific decision rules, helping the user to choose between a certain set of predetermined alternatives. To be noted that building such a system requires to

¹ Source : e-Shape deliverable 2.6 : Validated model of co-design process.

make explicit these decision rules, the level of precision expected and the underlying risks (for ex false alarm).

Ex: a system that integrates some functionalities to help trigger certain actions when threshold is exceeded.

- 3) **Scenario design support system:** monitoring system complemented with other customized tools helping the user to design new alternatives or operations, for example by the exploration of specific scenarios. To be noted that it differs from the decision support system as the latter only helps to choose between existing alternatives.

Ex: a system that integrates some functionalities to help explore new mitigation actions, regulations, etc.

- 4) **Specific service provision:** punctual advisory service, specific preliminary study, punctual information provision. Such service provision might be necessary as a first step before considering building more stabilized systems, in a temporary mode.

Ex: Preliminary scientific study on the possible correlation between air pollution episodes and visits to emergency departments.

But it can also concern permanent situations.

Ex: a targeted scientific partnership such as working on specific measurement and standardization protocols for specific pollutants.

- 5) **Information provision:** In some cases, information can be used as such directly by the user, we could then refer to a simple “information provision” or data brokering. It is for example the case when users are research communities. In this case, information could be complemented with access to other resources such as modelling resources.

- 6) **Design of a Supersite:** Supersite can be understood a digital infrastructure dedicated to specific local uses on top of which data cubes and/or other service can be implemented on an on-going basis as to answer evolving local needs.

Ex: designing a supersite for a city (e.g. Marseille) allows to establish a stable channel to provide the users with various types of services and data to address evolving needs related to various types of concerns (e.g. nature in Town, Energy, urban biodiversity, etc.)

2.1.3. Stakeholder to be involved (Color coding)

As various stakeholders can be involved in the co-design process, the outcomes diagram should make it clear who is to be involved in each action. This can be done by associating different colors with the different boxes corresponding to each outcome. For instance:

- Some actions may be **the responsibility of the service developer**, they can be associated with blue boxes.
- Some actions may be **the responsibility of the user**, they can be associated with green boxes.

Some actions may be **the responsibility of other partners**, they can be associated with yellow boxes.

- Some actions can have to be handled **jointly by different stakeholders**, they can be associated with red boxes.

Assigning accountability for the different actions is critical to ensure an effective follow-up on these actions and to give substance to the emerging resilient relationships.

2.1.4. Modalities for collaboration and objectives (Text within the boxes)

Each outcome of the co-design process can be understood as a specific project stream that can be started with the user or other potential stakeholder. Specific collaborative modalities can be associated with these projects have to clarify the key next steps to work on.

While the primary objective of the service developer might be to develop, in the end, an operational service, some preliminary collaborations or projects could be required and could take various forms. Therefore, technical collaboration is not the sole path to consider. Other forms of collaboration can result from the co-design process and that should be considered as to build resilient relationship with users, such as:

- Joint exploration of use cases, potential partners, etc.
- Joint search and/or application to public funding opportunities.
- Research project, to explore new scientific model, improve existing one or investigate the influence of some specific factors on a variable for instance.
- Internship or thesis to adapt a specific model of application to a precise context for instance.
- Common event of public joint communication to announce the collaboration and attract potential partners.
- Etc.

These modalities should be captured by the outcome framework in order to formalize and recognize collectively the interest of this potential project. The text description should inform on the collectively envisioned objectives for the activity.

2.1.5. Reading the outcomes diagram

The Figure 3 gives an illustrative instance of an outcome diagram filled at the end of a co-design process involving a service provider, a potential user and a potential partner.

Figure 2. Filled template for the Outcomes Diagram

Based on this diagram, the project portfolio resulting from the co-design process can be understood as follows:

- In a long-term perspective, the objective of the collaboration between the partners is to co-develop a monitoring system which could raise alert in case of extreme urban heat events.
- In the short-term, the partners agreed to jointly explore the existing regulatory frameworks and operational practices related to public communication and management of climate extremes, identifying where DestinE data and models could bring added analytical value.
- In the short-term, the partners will provide the user and service developer with dynamic ground temperature maps, and on midterm with climate forecast data related to extreme heat events.
- In mid- and long-term, the service provider would collaborate with the partner to design an extreme climate forecasting service and would also launch a PhD Thesis on mitigation actions to prevent extreme heat events.
- On midterm, the user would define a process to alert and protect the local population in case of extreme heat events.

As such, this diagram offers a consistent portfolio of actions nurturing a resilient on-going relationship between the three partners.

2.2. Dynamic perspective on the outcomes diagram

The outcomes diagram should be used in a dynamic perspective to support the resiliency of the relationships established through co-design. This dynamic perspective can be understood in two ways.

2.2.1. Building a dynamic project portfolio

As far as possible, the actions and projects that constitute the co-design outcomes should be defined as to support the progression of the collaboration. This means that links should be established between the different actions in order to stage from the outset a fertile ground for follow-up and resilient relationship.

It is likely that different project streams corresponding to different long-term objectives will be identified, and for each of them it is advisable to think of intermediate stages in the short and medium term. This has the advantage of ensuring an ongoing relationship and regular points of contact between the stakeholders. It also has the advantage of breaking down tasks so that they can be worked on in parallel and revised as unforeseen circumstances or new opportunities arise.

Typically, the outcomes diagram shown in Figure 4 offers a great instance of a portfolio of actions that serves a common long-term objective based on intermediate actions by the three stakeholders on short and mid-terms.

2.2.2. Dynamic Adaptation and Follow-up Actions

Each workshop should not only refine existing services but also generate actionable insights to guide future co-design efforts. As the co-design process unfolds, gaps in knowledge, newly identified stakeholders, or evolving user needs may emerge, prompting the need for additional workshops or alternative co-design activities tailored to these changing circumstances.

To capture this, it is essential to document follow-up actions, including the identification of new stakeholders or actors to engage, areas where further knowledge or skills are needed, and recommendations for future workshops with specific focus areas or participants.

To maximize the value of each session, it is important to debrief after every workshop, using the insights gained to identify opportunities for improvement or expansion. This approach ensures the co-design process remains dynamic and adaptive, evolving alongside the needs and complexities of the user ecosystem.

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